

The role of authoritative parenting and self-regulation in controlling adolescent aggressiveness

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ABSTRACT

Seeing the many cases of adolescent violence that occurred in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, this study was interested in examining the suitability of authoritative parenting and self-regulation abilities to the level of adolescent aggressiveness. The subjects of this study were 154 class XII students of State Senior High School 1 Sleman. The sample selection was obtained using a stratified random sampling technique. The aim is to obtain student representation from each class. Researchers use the scale as the main tool in obtaining research data on aggressiveness, authoritative parenting and self-regulation. The data was then analyzed using multiple linear regression with the SPSS V26 program. The results of the analysis showed that, simultaneously, authoritative parenting and self-regulation were very significant in suppressing the emergence of aggressiveness in adolescents ($F=51.76$ and $Sig.=.000$). Then, both authoritative parenting ($Beta=-.37$ with $Sig.=.000$) and self-regulation ($Beta=-.35$ with $Sig.=.000$) both were able to have a significant effect on adolescent aggressiveness partially. The conclusion is that adolescents need authoritative parenting at this phase; this is necessary to avoid the emergence or development of aggressiveness in adolescents. Besides that, adolescents must also be equipped with self-regulation skills because most activities are carried out without parental supervision.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a prone period to having problems. Frequently encountered problems among them are emotional instability. This condition makes teenagers aggressive, so it is not uncommon for teenagers to show behavior against (both physically and verbally) [1]. According to research by Myers and Twenge [2], aggressiveness is a behavior carried out intentionally to annoy or hurt others; if the individual harms another person unintentionally, the behavior does not include aggressiveness.

Every individual has a basically for aggressiveness in essence, but it is very unfortunate if this action is carried out by students and develops in the world of education [3]; this is because it is contrary to

the nature of education itself which aims to educate the nation's morals. Nevertheless, student violence cases continue to occur [4]. Data collected by the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) shows that throughout 2019 there were at least 153 complaints of cases of violence against students [5].

Based on the education unit, high school students have a higher percentage of aggressiveness which is 39%, compared to 22% for junior high school students [6]. This aggression (high school students) is generally carried out by senior students who want to discipline their juniors or by students who try to maintain self-esteem because they want to be recognized by each other that they or their group are the best; In fact, this harassment often happens to students between schools, which leads to brawls [7].

Refers to public health; basically, no one wants the presence of aggressiveness in any context in society, especially in the world of education, which should be able to solve problems in an educative way. However, as stated by Freire [8], it cannot be denied that education also contains elements of oppression and that schools are places where violence occurs. Schools as educational institutions seem to have two opposite sides of the face; on the one hand, the school is a place to organize learning activities. On the other hand, the school can also be used as a place to commit acts of violence.

Yogyakarta (Indonesia), as an education city, is also inseparable from cases of violence; even the level of violence occupies the highest position in Indonesia when viewed from the ratio of the number of cases divided by the population [9]–[12]. Cases of violence often occur include brawls between school gangs and street violence (*klitih*), as just happened on September 29th, 2021, in South Ring Road, Bantul. A brawl between school gangs involving Stepiro's gang from Yogyakarta City high school and SASE's gang from Bantul high school. As a result of the incident, one member of the SASE gang with the initials MKA died, and one person with the initials RAW suffered serious injuries and had to be rushed to the hospital [13].

Furthermore, the *klitih* actions that have terrorized the people of Yogyakarta in recent years occurred again at Bantul on 2022. A group of teenagers consisting of five people carried out the *klitih* action, which caused the death of 18-year-old student victim. According to the joint team of director of general criminal investigation (Dirreskrim) Polda DIY and Pores Bantul have succeeded in securing the five *klitih* perpetrators; the perpetrator's motive for carrying out the *klitih* action was to find a fighting opponent [14]. Later in the same month, the Banguntapan Police, Bantul, managed to arrest four teenagers at the East Ringroad, Banguntapan, Bantul, who were about to carry out the *klitih* action. Based on Supriyatna's statement, the four teenagers were members of the Mavastra Gang who had made an appointment with the Registor Gang to fight on Jalan Wonosari Km 6, but because the Registor Gang did not come, the Registor Gang finally decided to look for enemies around the East Ringroad. At that time, instead of getting prey, the Registor Gang was caught by a patrol from the Banguntapan Police [15]. Even at the beginning of 2023, during January-February, the police received 42 reports of *klitih* cases in the Yogyakarta City to Sleman areas where the perpetrators were teenagers or minors (students) [16].

According to the Commissioner. Pol. Yulianto, is not surprising that in Yogyakarta, there are frequent brawls between school gangs and *klitih* because almost all high schools in DIY have student gangs; this was discovered after the Yogyakarta Regional Police collected data from the Resort Police and Regional Police regarding the existence of student gangs in all districts and cities of Yogyakarta. These gangs include NCZ (gang from SMAN 2 Yogyakarta), TNT (gang from SMAN 3 Yogyakarta), SMC (gang from SMAN 4 Yogyakarta), ROEVER (gang from SMAN 5 Yogyakarta), DEPAZTER (gang from SMAN 6 Yogyakarta), GBZ (gang from SMAN 7 Yogyakarta), CBZ (gang from SMAN 8 Yogyakarta), GANZA (gang from SMAN 9 Yogyakarta), SMT (gang from SMAN 10 Yogyakarta), REM (gang from SMAN 11 Yogyakarta), NEXAZ (gang from SMAN 1 Sleman), RESPECT PRAZA (gang from SMAN 1 Prambanan), SOC'S (gang from SMAN 1 Kalasan), BBC (gang from SMAN 1 Depok), BOSSE (gang from SMAN 1 Seyegan), ROOSTER (gang from SMAN 2 Bantul), STIMCO (gang from SMAN 3 Bantul), SASE (SMAN 1 Sewon) and many more [17].

The presence of these school gangs can certainly increase the number of cases and victims of violence committed by students; therefore, AKP Riko Sanjaya appeals to the community, especially parents of students, to be able to look after and educate their children [18]. According to Tirtowisastro (an expert on the Sociologist of Crime from UGM), the handling of violent acts committed by several students cannot only be imposed on the school (BK teacher) and law enforcement officers (police). Efforts to break this violence must start from the family level because the family is the first bastion that instills spiritual values and social norms to minimize students' actions that can hurt others (aggressiveness). Students who are not equipped with good morals will very easily model the behavior of other people they admire, regardless of whether the behavior is harmful or not [19].

According to Santrock [20], educating high school students (adolescents) is not as easy as educating elementary students (children), although it cannot be said that educating elementary students is very easy. In this phase, high school students have very high curiosity, a need for recognition from the surrounding environment, and a tendency to model the behavior of others [21]. Without proper control from parents, students can fall into juvenile delinquency [22]. Therefore, parents need to adopt a parenting pattern

appropriate to students' developmental stage in their teens [23]. One type of pattern that is believed to be able to minimize the emergence of student aggressiveness in adolescence is authoritative parenting [24].

The authoritative parenting style is a parenting style that gives adolescents the freedom to explore themselves according to the boundaries set by society (social norms) [25]. Baumrind [26] introduces the authoritative parenting style as a free parenting style (parents give adolescents the freedom to make decisions about themselves) but firm (adolescents must be responsible for the freedom granted by their parents). Parents who apply an authoritative parenting style try to direct the activities of adolescents so that they can contribute to society and have a positive meaning for themselves; thus, adolescents are directed to be part of society and have a social role in society. Parents also explain why some rules in society must be obeyed together; the goal is that teenagers do not carry out activities that can harm other people and disrupt public order [27], [28]. In addition, when adolescents make mistakes, parents try to allow adolescents to explain their behavior or decisions so that positive communication is built between parents and adolescents [29].

According to reports from several adolescent development researchers, students in the adolescent phase tend to prefer and want an authoritative parenting style to be applied by their parents. The reason is that students want to be appreciated and supported by adults every step of the way; moreover, in this phase, students feel capable enough to choose and make good decisions [30], [31]. Although in some cases, teenagers show an attitude of not being able to bear the consequences of their decisions [32], [33]. However, the important thing that needs to be emphasized at this phase is the self-confidence, self-esteem and self-concept that adolescent students need to have; because with this set of psychological attributes, adolescent students tend to be better able to control their attitudes and behavior so as not to disturb or hurt others (therefore, by applying authoritative parenting, parents will more easily control and direct adolescent students to follow social norms in society) [34], [35].

In addition to the need for control from parents, the students must equip themselves with self-control skills (self-regulation) so that they avoid wanting to hurt or vent their anger on others. According to Thompson [36], this needs to be emphasized because parents cannot always control student activities outside the home with their friends. Self-regulation is the process of evaluating and modifying the emotional reactions that students are experiencing [37]. This ability is related to how students prevent the emergence of excessive negative emotions and maintain positive emotions that they want to display to other people or the environment [38].

One of the main reasons why every student needs to have self-regulation is because this ability can suppress the emergence of aggressiveness [39]. The available evidence shows that students' inability to control angry emotions will result in physical and verbal aggressiveness towards others around them [40]. Not only angry emotions but failure to regulate sad emotions can also result in the emergence of aggressiveness (generally only verbal, not physical) to vent their sadness. Therefore, this ability is crucial to keeping mentally healthy and positive [41]. Based on the description of the background, the researcher is interested in testing "whether adolescents need the appropriateness of parenting style (authoritative parenting) and self-regulation ability in controlling the emergence of aggressiveness."

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants and procedures

The population in this study were all students of class XII State Senior High School 1 Sleman, amounting to 252 students. There are two majors in State Senior High School 1 Sleman, the mathematics and natural sciences (MIPA) department, which consists of five classes (MIPA 1, MIPA 2, MIPA 3, MIPA 4, MIPA 5) and the social studies (IPS) major, which consists of two classes (IPS 1, IPS 2). Researchers took 154 students as research samples with a stratified random sampling technique; thus, each class is represented by 22 randomly selected students. The steps are: i) the researcher determines the number of samples from the entire population using the Slovin formula with an error rate of 5%; ii) the researcher calculates the number of students needed to be able to represent the population unit; the way is to divide the number of samples by the total number of classes (154/7); and iii) the researchers randomly selected several students from each class to represent the population unit.

2.2. Validity and reliability of research instruments

This study uses a Likert model scale with four alternative answers (strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree) as the main instrument for obtaining empirical data on aggressiveness, authoritative parenting and self-regulation. The three scales are the result of their preparation by the researcher. Each item is divided into two types of statements: favorable and unfavorable. The preparation of the aggressiveness scale refers to the types of aggressiveness according to Buss and Perry [42], which consist of physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger, and hostility. After the reliability test was carried out, 20 obtained items

were ready to be used for research with a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.874. The preparation of the authoritative parenting scale refers to aspects of authoritative parenting according to Baumrind [26], which consist of warmth, control and communication. After the reliability test, 24 obtained items were ready to be used for research with a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.917. The preparation of the self-regulation scale refers to a dimension of self-regulation according to Polnariiev [43], which consists of attention regulation, emotion regulation and behavior regulation. After the reliability test was carried out, 15 obtained items were ready to be used for research with a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.857.

2.3. Data analysis

The data analysis used in this research is a multiple linear regression analysis with SPSS 26 program. Multiple linear regression analysis is one of the analyzes in parametric statistics which require the fulfilment of assumptions (normality, linearity, and multicollinearity) before testing the hypothesis. There are three research hypotheses: i) there is a simultaneous effect of authoritative parenting and self-regulation on student aggressiveness; ii) partially, there is the influence of authoritative parenting on student aggressiveness; and iii) partially, there is an influence of self-regulation on student aggressiveness.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis aims to provide a general description of the data obtained by researchers in the field. The data used are empirical and hypothetical; later, this analysis will display the mean score, minimum score, maximum score, and standard deviation of each research variable (aggressiveness, authoritative parenting, and self-regulation). The results of the descriptive analysis can be seen in Table 1.

Data from descriptive analysis (mean score, minimum score, maximum score, and standard deviation) will be used by researchers in categorizing; this analysis determines the high and low scores obtained by the subject on each variable. The score will be classified using high, medium, and low. The following are the results of the categorization of each research variable.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis

Variable	Empirical data				Hypothetical data			
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Aggressiveness	42.89	6.06	28	57	50	10	20	80
Authoritative parenting	68.18	6.74	50	81	60	12	24	96
Self-regulation	44.45	8.73	28	60	37.5	7.5	15	60

3.1.1. Categorization of aggressiveness data

From the results of the categorization of aggressiveness scores obtained, as many as 29.22% of adolescents are in the high category, and 70.78% of adolescents are in the medium category. This means that the average research subject has a moderate level of aggressiveness which tends to be low. The results of the aggressiveness score categorization can be seen in Table 2.

3.1.2. Categorization of authoritative parenting data

From the results of the categorization of authoritative parenting scores, it was obtained that 37.01% of adolescents were in the high category, and 62.99% of adolescents were in the medium category. Which means that most (on average) research subjects are in moderate authoritative parenting but tend to be high. The results of the categorization of authoritative parenting scores can be seen in Table 3.

Table 2. Categorization of aggressiveness data

Norm	Frequency	Weight (%)	Category
$X \geq 60$	-	-	High
$40 \leq X < 60$	109	70.78%	Medium
$X < 40$	45	29.22%	Low

Table 3. Categorization of authoritative parenting data

Norm	Frequency	Weight (%)	Category
$X \geq 72$	57	37.01%	High
$48 \leq X < 72$	97	62.99%	Medium
$X < 48$	-	-	Low

3.1.3. Categorization of self-regulatory data

From the results of the categorization of self-regulation scores, as many as 42.21% of adolescents were in the high category, and 57.79% of adolescents were in the medium category. This means that the average research subjects have a moderate level of emotional regulation but tend to be high. The results of the categorization of self-regulation scores can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Categorization of self-regulatory data

Norm	Frequency	Weight (%)	Category
$X \geq 45$	65	42.21	High
$30 \leq X < 45$	89	57.79	Medium
$X < 30$	-	-	Low

3.2. Classic assumption test

The assumption test is a requirement that must be met in performing parametric statistical analysis. In multiple linear regression parametric analysis, several assumptions that must be met include the normality test, linearity test, and multicollinearity test. The following are the results of the analysis of each assumption test.

3.2.1. Normality test

The normality test aims to determine whether the sample used is normally distributed. The rules used in this test are the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS-Z) technique; data is said to be representative when the value of Sig. > .05. From the results of the normality test, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z score obtained on aggressiveness, authoritative parenting and self-regulation were .88, 1.05, 1.23 with Sig. 0.425, .217 and .100 ($p > .05$); meaning that the research sample is able to represent the population. The results of the normality test can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Normality test

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	Sig.	Interpretation
Aggressiveness	.88	.425	Linear
Authoritative parenting	1.05	.217	Linear
Self-regulation	1.23	.100	Linear

3.2.2. Linearity test

The linearity test aims to see a linear line connecting the independent variable with the dependent variable. The rule used in this test is the F linearity technique; data is said to be linear when the value of Sig. < .05. From the results of linearity testing, the F linearity scores obtained between authoritative parenting with aggressiveness and self-regulation with aggressiveness are 132.39 and 101.41 with Sig values for all variables of .000 ($p < .05$); meaning that each independent variable in this study is linearly connected with the dependent variable. The results of the linearity test can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Linearity test

Variable	F Linearity	Sig.	Interpretation
Authoritative parenting with aggressiveness	132.39	.000	Linear
Self-regulation with aggressiveness	101.41	.000	Linear

3.2.3. Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether there is a similarity in function between the independent variables and other independent variables; to determine the presence or absence of multicollinearity, you can look at the tolerance and VIF values. The rules used are the tolerance value > 0.1 and the VIF value < 10. The results of the multicollinearity test show that the tolerance and VIF values in authoritative parenting and self-regulation are .669 and 1.494, meaning that each independent variable proposed in this study does not occur in multicollinearity. The results of the multicollinearity test analysis can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Multicollinearity test

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Interpretation
Authoritative parenting	.669	1.494	There is no multicollinearity
Self-regulation	.669	1.494	There is no multicollinearity

3.3. Hypothesis testing

3.3.1. Major hypothesis

The results of multiple linear regression analysis for the first hypothesis obtained that the F value in authoritative parenting and self-regulation on aggressiveness was 51.76 with a Sig value of .000 ($p < 0.01$); that is, simultaneously there is a very significant influence of authoritative parenting and self-regulation on adolescent aggressiveness. The two independent variables' contribution (R square) is 40.7%. The results of multiple linear regression analysis for the first hypothesis can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Multiple regression analysis

Variable	F	R Square	Sig.	Interpretation
Authoritative parenting and self-regulation with aggressiveness	51.76	.407	.000	There is a very significant effect

3.3.2. Minor hypothesis

The results of multiple linear regression analysis for the second hypothesis obtained the Beta value of authoritative parenting on the aggressiveness of $-.37$ with a Sig value of .000 ($p < 0.01$); this means that there is a very significant negative (two-way) effect authoritative parenting on aggressiveness so that the better the application of authoritative parenting provided by parents, the lower the possibility of aggressive. Furthermore, the results of multiple linear regression analysis for the third hypothesis obtained the value of Beta self-regulation on the aggressiveness of $-.35$ with a Sig value of .000 ($p < 0.01$); this means that there is a very significant negative (two-way) effect self-regulation on aggressiveness so that the better the self-regulation abilities of adolescents, the lower the level of adolescent aggressiveness. The results of multiple linear regression analysis for the second and third hypotheses can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Partial correlation analysis

Variable	Beta	Sig.	Interpretation
Authoritative parenting with aggressiveness	$-.37$.000	There is a very significant negative effect
Self-regulation with aggressiveness	$-.35$.000	There is a very significant negative effect

3.3.3. Coefficient of determination

The researcher uses (1) to determine the effective contribution of each independent variable to aggressiveness. The results of calculations based on this formula are known that the contribution of authoritative parenting to aggressiveness is 21.1%, while the contribution of self-regulation to aggressiveness is 19.6%; from these results, it is known that authoritative parenting is an independent variable that has a more dominant contribution to aggressiveness. The results of the calculation of the effective contribution of each independent variable can be seen in Table 10.

$$SE = \text{standardized coefficients beta} \times \text{zero order} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Table 10. Coefficient of determination

Variable	Beta	Zero order	%	Interpretation
Authoritative parenting	$-.37$	$-.57$	100%	21.1%
Self-regulation	$-.35$	$-.35$	100%	19.6%

The phenomenon of aggressiveness among high school students is no stranger. This behavior brings negative impacts and significant losses in various aspects of life. However, not all high school students have high aggressiveness, as shown by the results of this study (categorization) that the level of aggressiveness of State Senior High School 1 Sleman students is low. The low level of aggressiveness is not without reason; students are in authoritative parenting and have pretty good self-regulation abilities. Researchers use empirical data to look for categorization to determine the actual conditions in the field.

The results of the categorization analysis in this study (low level of student aggressiveness) are not in line with the researcher's initial assumption that students of State Senior High School 1 Sleman tend to have a relatively high level of aggressiveness, low authoritative parenting, and low self-regulation; this initial assumption was based on the violent acts that have been carried out by the NEXAZ gang (State Senior High School 1 Sleman) so far [44]–[46]. Data collection conducted online (based on the school's policy because the students' learning process is still online) is believed to be one of the causes of this discrepancy. Researchers cannot confirm whether students answered according to their original conditions, so there is a possibility of bias in this study, namely where students do fake good (when students are faced with certain statements that have a negative meaning, the answer will lead to a positive).

Furthermore, there are three results of the analysis that the researcher will discuss in this discussion; first, the results obtained from multiple linear regression analysis on the first hypothesis show a very significant influence of authoritative parenting and self-regulation on the aggressiveness of high school students. These results indicate that the first hypothesis proposed by the researcher is accepted. In terms of novelty, researchers have not found research similar to this study, both from the proposed independent variables, research subjects, to the location of the research carried out; thus, this study is the only literature that discusses the influence of authoritative parenting and self-regulation on student aggressiveness State Senior High School 1 Sleman.

Second, the partial correlation analysis results on the second hypothesis show a very significant effect of authoritative parenting on the aggressiveness of high school students. These results indicate that the second hypothesis that the researcher proposes is accepted. Parents have an essential role in child development in their teens [47]. In this phase, high school students need guidance from adults who can reflect on the youth's freedom to behave [48]. Conformity between parenting patterns and adolescent characters is needed because the choice of parenting patterns will determine the tendency of adolescents to behave [49]. The impact of this discrepancy (parenting pattern) will lead to deviant behaviors such as acts of violence or brawls, destruction of public facilities, looting, and other behaviors that harm others [50].

Authoritative parenting is child-centered, with higher warmth and lower control [51]. This style offers tolerant or flexible parenting so parents can quickly get along with teenagers (parents act as friends) and strongly support teenagers' freedom of expression [52]. Although parents have weak rules that allow teens to decide what to do on their own, parents provide full support and warmth; this is done to facilitate the great curiosity of adolescents, the need for adolescents for social roles (responsibility), and recognition or appreciation for their achievements [53]. Parents who adopt authoritative parenting will avoid verbal or physical punishment; parents want teenagers to try new things and learn from their mistakes [54]. Parents do not demand teenagers with such high standards but try to build comfort in communicating [55]. Parents are ready to share information and experiences to foster warmth of affection and openness between adolescents and parents [56].

Authoritative parenting produces a series of benefits, such as forming creativity and a sense of responsibility in adolescents [57]; thus, adolescents will have independence in making choices, be able to control behavior and make decisions and be able to choose good associations for their development. This experience will increase self-confidence, self-esteem, and problem-solving abilities [58]. A degree of independence predicts lower aggressiveness and other deviant behaviors [59]. Adolescents will judge their parents with dignity and have high respect because they have given them the freedom to make choices and support every decision [60].

Third, the partial correlation analysis results on hypothesis three show a very significant effect of self-regulation on the aggressiveness of high school students. These results indicate that the third hypothesis that the researcher proposes is accepted. Self-regulation is one of the most influential and tested theories in explaining the mechanism of growth of aggressiveness and other deviant behavior in adolescents [61]. According to this theory, self-regulation can inhibit adolescents' desire to commit deviant actions [62]. Until now, several previous researchers have consistently found that low self-regulation affects the emergence of aggressiveness [63], [64].

Adolescents with self-regulation fully know all their thoughts and actions [65]. Adolescents can override immediate impulses that have long-term negative consequences [66], whereas adolescents without self-regulation cannot avoid wanting to hurt others. Adolescents tend to have a selfish attitude, temperamental and are less concerned with the conditions around them, and every action is full of risks that can harm themselves and others [67], [68]. According to Manzoni and Schwarzenegger [69], this action does not produce positive benefits for others or himself but merely seeks sensation and momentary satisfaction (without considering the painful consequences of negative actions). Therefore, self-regulation is considered a vital ability needed by adolescents to suppress the emergence of aggressiveness.

Self-regulation is a personal attribute obtained by adolescents in childhood due to the selection of parenting styles that are appropriate to their developmental stage [70]. Parents who use violence in educating

their children tend not to be able to teach self-regulation [71]. The violence is a manifestation of the parents' low self-regulation ability; consequently, the child will seek an outlet (revenge) in the future [72]. Thus, it can be said that authoritative parenting and self-regulation cannot be separated in the development of human behavior. These two factors contribute to each other in minimizing the growth of aggressiveness. The implication is that, through the results of this study, it is hoped that researchers can provide input for the school (especially State Senior High School 1 Sleman) to socialize parenting knowledge to parents (considering that not all parents understand parenting) and also advise the school to equip their students with self-regulation skills (which allows students to be able to control themselves when in or dealing with conditions that trigger the emergence of aggressiveness).

Finally, the researcher will discuss the limitations of this study; namely, the researcher cannot collect data directly or offline due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which requires students to carry out online learning activities. This condition makes the researcher unable to ascertain whether students understand the statements in the scale of the research intended by the researcher so that the impact is believed to affect the results of the reliability of the research scale and descriptive analysis. Thus, if the next researcher wants to do replication research (both in the same location or in a different location), the researcher needs to minimize or overcome the limitations in this study, such as facilitating students to be able to carry out scale filling through the zoom or google meet application which allows researchers to control the filling of the research scale directly, involving several class coordinators or school organizations to coordinate all students participating in this research and asking for help from several homeroom teachers to assist in the implementation of filling out the scale at the beginning of the event.

4. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that all hypotheses proposed by the researcher are accepted. First, there is simultaneously a very significant influence of authoritative parenting and self-regulation on student aggressiveness. Second, there is a significant effect of authoritative parenting on student aggressiveness. Third, partially there is a very significant effect of self-regulation on student aggressiveness. Thus, the results of this study emphasize the importance of the role of parents in providing appropriate care for their children and not necessarily giving the full burden to the school in educating their children; when parents can work with the school to jointly educate their children to have good manners, these can indirectly help local governments suppress the emergence of deviant adolescent behavior (especially in Yogyakarta City).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Gallarin and I. Alonso-Arbiol, "Parenting practices, parental attachment and aggressiveness in adolescence: A predictive model," *Journal of Adolescence*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1601–1610, 2012. doi: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.07.002.
- [2] D. G. Myers and J. M. Twenge, *Social psychology*, 13th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education, 2019.
- [3] W. A. Warburton and C. A. Anderson, "Aggression, social psychology of," in *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 2nd ed., J. D. Wright, Ed., Oxford: Elsevier, 2015, pp. 373–380. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.24002-6.
- [4] G. Intan, "KPAI: Cases of violence against children in education increased in 2018," VOA Indonesia (in Indonesian), 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.voaindonesia.com/a/kpai-kasus-kekerasan-anak-dalam-pendidikan-meningkat-tahun-2018/4718166.html> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [5] N. A. Widadio, "KPAI recorded 153 cases of physical and psychological violence in schools in 2019," Anadolu Agency Turki (in Indonesian), 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aa.com.tr/id/nasional/kpai-catat-153-kasus-kekerasan-fisik-dan-psikis-di-sekolah-pada-2019/1688253> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [6] "Throughout 2019, KPAI received 153 complaints of physical violence against students," *Pikiran Rakyat* (in Indonesian), 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pikiran-rakyat.com/pendidikan/pr-01329204/sepanjang-2019-kpai-terima-153-aduan-kekerasan-fisik-terhadap-siswa> (accessed: Nov. 22, 2024).
- [7] T. Budirahayu and N. Susan, "Violence at school and its root causes," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Contemporary Social and Political Affairs (IcoCSPA 2017)*, Paris, France: Atlantis Press, 2018. doi: 10.2991/icoSPA-17.2018.3.
- [8] P. Freire, "Pädagogik der unterdrückten," in *Handbuch Bildungs- und Erziehungssoziologie*, U. Bauer, U. H. Bittlingmayer, and A. Scherr, Eds., Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2022, pp. 365–377. doi: 10.1007/978-3-658-30903-9_79.
- [9] A. Nasiruddin, "Expose data on the handling of victims of violence against women and children in the Special Region of Yogyakarta," Dinas Pemberdayaan Perempuan Perlindungan Anak dan Pengendalian Penduduk Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. [Online]. Available: <https://dp3ap2.jogjaprovo.go.id/berita/detail/582-ekspose-data-penanganan-korban-kekerasan-terhadap-perempuan-dan-anak-daerah-istimewa-yogyakarta-tahu> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [10] Statistics Indonesia (Badan Pusat Statistik/BPS), "Criminal statistics 2020," Jakarta: Badan Pusat Statistik (in Indonesian), 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bps.go.id/id/publication/2020/11/17/0f2dfc46761281f68f11afb1/statistik-kriminal-2020.html> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [11] Statistics Indonesia (Badan Pusat Statistik/BPS), "Criminal statistics 2021," Jakarta: Badan Pusat Statistik (in Indonesian), 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bps.go.id/id/publication/2021/12/15/8d1bc84d2055e99feed39986/statistik-kriminal-2021.html> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [12] Statistics Indonesia (Badan Pusat Statistik/BPS), "Criminal statistics 2022," Jakarta: Badan Pusat Statistik (in Indonesian), 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bps.go.id/id/publication/2022/11/30/4022d3351bf3a05aa6198065/statistik-kriminal-2022.html> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).

- [13] Newswire, "A brawl between 2 student gangs in Bantul, 1 person died from a stab wound," *Bisnis.com*, (in Indonesian), 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://semarang.bisnis.com/read/20211109/535/1463759/tawuran-2-geng-pelajar-di-bantul-1-orang-tewas-terkena-bacokan> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [14] D. Dwiarti, "In Klitih's action, the police arrested 5 perpetrators in Jogja, who killed a high school student," *Pikiran Rakyat* (in Indonesian), Apr. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://seputartangsel.pikiran-rakyat.com/nasional/pr-144229935/aksi-klitih-polisi-amankan-5-pelaku-di-jogja-yang-tewaskan-seorang-pelajar-sma> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [15] H. P. Aji, "Teenage brawls rife, the police fail to clash with the Resistor Gang and Mavastra, the location is near Daffa's death," *Harian Merapi* (in Indonesian), Apr. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.harianmerapi.com/peristiwa/pr-403163019/tawuran-remaja-marak-polisi-gagalkan-bentrok-geng-resistor-dan-mavastra-lokasinya-dekat-tewasnya-daffa> (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [16] "Police: 42 cases of Klitih occurred during January-February 2023," *CNN Indonesia* (in Indonesian), 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cnnindonesia.com/nasional/20230327094425-12-929698/polisi-42-kasus-klitih-terjadi-selama-januari-februari-2023> (accessed: May 12, 2023).
- [17] L. Subarkah, "Polda: Almost all high schools in DIY have student gangs," *Harian Jogja* (in Indonesian), Nov. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://jogjapolitan.harianjogja.com/read/2021/11/10/510/1087896/polda-hampir-semua-sma-di-diy-punya-geng-pelajar> (accessed: Feb. 05, 2022).
- [18] A. Indah, "The klitih case is still rife in Yogyakarta, the police are urging parents to control children's activities," *Tribun Jogja* (in Indonesian), 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://jogja.tribunnews.com/2021/02/05/kasus-klitih-masih-marak-di-di-yogyakarta-polisi-imbau-orangtua-kontrol-aktivitas-anak?page=all> (accessed: Dec. 16, 2022).
- [19] "Handling klitih is not only the responsibility of the police," UGM (in Indonesian), Jan. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://ugm.ac.id/id/berita/18933-penanganan-klitih-bukan-hanya-tanggung-jawab-kepolisian/> (accessed: Dec. 21, 2022).
- [20] J. Santrock, *A topical approach to life-span development*. New York: McGraw Hill Education, 2020.
- [21] M. Gölcük and S. K. Berument, "The relationship between negative parenting and child and maternal temperament," *Current Psychology*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 3596–3608, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s12144-019-00307-9.
- [22] O. L. O. Lokoyi, "Parenting styles as correlates of aggressive behaviour among in-school adolescent with mild intellectual disability," *Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 94–100, 2015, doi: 10.11648/j.pbs.20150403.12.
- [23] A. P. Danzig, M. W. Dyson, T. M. Olino, R. S. Lupton, and D. N. Klein, "Positive parenting interacts with child temperament and negative parenting to predict children's socially appropriate behavior," *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 411–435, May 2015, doi: 10.1521/jscp.2015.34.5.411.
- [24] L. D. Bougher, "Revisiting parental influence in individual political development: Democratic parenting in adolescence," *Applied Developmental Science*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 284–300, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1080/10888691.2017.1288125.
- [25] T. J. Schofield and J. M. Weaver, "Democratic parenting beliefs and observed parental sensitivity: Reciprocal influences between coparents," *Journal of Family Psychology*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 509–515, 2016, doi: 10.1037/fam0000166.
- [26] D. Baumrind, "Current patterns of parental authority," *Developmental Psychology*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–103, Jan. 1971, doi: 10.1037/h0030372.
- [27] P. Pinjai and S. Damrongpanit, "Effects of democratic parenting and teaching activities on high school students' global citizenship: A multilevel structural equation model with student factors as mediators," *European Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1569–1580, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.12973/eu-jer.9.4.1569.
- [28] S. Oryan and J. Gastil, "Democratic parenting: paradoxical messages in democratic parent education theories," *International Review of Education*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 113–129, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11159-013-9351-7.
- [29] M. Miklikowska and H. Hurme, "Democracy begins at home: Democratic parenting and adolescents' support for democratic values," *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 541–557, 2011, doi: 10.1080/17405629.2011.576856.
- [30] R. Xiong, S. De Li, and Y. Xia, "A longitudinal study of authoritative parenting, juvenile delinquency and crime victimization among Chinese adolescents," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 4, p. 1405, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17041405.
- [31] E. Onsono, M. K. Mwenje, and P. Githui, "The influence of parenting style on male juvenile delinquency: A case of Kamiti Youth Correction and Training Center (KYCTC), Kiambu County, Kenya," *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 21–29, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.24018/ejsocial.2021.1.3.44.
- [32] M. J. De la Torre-Cruz, M. C. García-Linares, and P. F. Casanova-Arias, "Relaciones entre Estilos Educativos Parentales y Agresividad en Adolescentes," *Electronic Journal of Research in Education Psychology*, vol. 12, no. 32, pp. 147–170, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.14204/ejrep.32.13118.
- [33] K. Yakin, N. Laily, and P. Amelasasih, "The effect of parenting perceptions (authoritative, authoritative, permissive) with adolescent's delay," *Journal Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik Engineering, Social Science, and Health International Conference*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 880–889, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.30587/umgshic.v1i2.3490.
- [34] A. F. Perez-Gramaje, O. F. Garcia, M. Reyes, E. Serra, and F. Garcia, "Parenting styles and aggressive adolescents: Relationships with self-esteem and personal maladjustment," *The European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–10, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.5093/ejpalc2020a1.
- [35] S. Deshmukh, "Effect of Pragma Yoga and Pranakarshana Pranayama on self-concept level of juvenile delinquents," *Dev Sanskriti Interdisciplinary International Journal*, vol. 17, pp. 57–61, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.36018/dsij.v17i1.186.
- [36] R. A. Thompson, "Socialization of emotion and emotion regulation in the family," in *Handbook of emotion regulation*, 2nd ed., New York, NY, US: The Guilford Press, 2014, pp. 173–186.
- [37] E. B. Hurlock, *Developmental Psychology: A Life-span Approach*. Erlangga, 2016.
- [38] D. Smeijers, M. Benbouriche, and C. Garofalo, "The association between emotion, social information processing, and aggressive behavior: A systematic review," *European Psychologist*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 81–91, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1027/1016-9040/a000395.
- [39] J. L. Cooley and P. J. Fite, "Peer victimization and forms of aggression during middle childhood: The role of emotion regulation," *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 535–546, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s10802-015-0051-6.
- [40] T. Robertson, M. Daffern, and R. S. Bucks, "Emotion regulation and aggression," *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 72–82, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.avb.2011.09.006.
- [41] T. N. Sullivan, S. W. Helms, W. Kliewer, and K. L. Goodman, "Associations between sadness and anger regulation coping, emotional expression, and physical and relational aggression among urban adolescents," *Social Development*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 30–51, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9507.2008.00531.x.
- [42] A. H. Buss and M. Perry, "The aggression questionnaire," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 452–459, Sep. 1992, doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.63.3.452.
- [43] B. A. Polnariiev, *Dynamics of preschoolers' self-regulation: Viewed through the lens of conflict resolution strategies during peer free-play paperback*. London: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, 2010.

- [44] W. C. Kusuma, "School gangs and identity (Study of the Nexaz gang at SMAN 1 Sleman)," (in Indonesian), Unpublished Thesis, Universitas Gadjah Mada, 2010.
- [45] W. D. Putri, "The number of teenage brawls in Sleman is getting higher," *Republika* (in Indonesian), Mar. 2015. [Online]. Available: https://news.republika.co.id/berita/nkzpm5/angka-tawuran-remaja-di-sleman-semakin-tinggi#google_vignette (accessed: Dec. 12, 2022).
- [46] N. Sucahyo, "School gangs, Yogya and bloody violence," *VOA Indonesia* (in Indonesian), 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.voaindonesia.com/a/geng-sekolah-yogya-dan-aksi-kekerasan-berdarah-/6523750.html> (Accessed: Sep. 03, 2022).
- [47] S. D. Li, T.-H. Liu, and Y. Xia, "A comparative study of parenting practices and juvenile delinquency between China and the United States," *Deviant Behavior*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 636–651, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1080/01639625.2022.2081102.
- [48] E. Avcı and R. Sak, "The relationship between parenting styles and fourth graders' levels of empathy and aggressiveness," *Current Psychology*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 510–522, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s12144-018-9959-7.
- [49] J. Hofer and B. Spengler, "How negative parenting might hamper identity development: Spontaneous aggressiveness and personal belief in a just world," *Self and Identity*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 117–139, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1080/15298868.2018.1541026.
- [50] B. Torres-Gomez, I. Alonso-Arbiol, and M. Gallarin, "Attachment to parents and aggressiveness in adopted adolescents: A multi-sample comparison study," *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, vol. 30, no. S1, pp. 46–54, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1111/jora.12463.
- [51] M. S. Eastin, B. S. Greenberg, and L. Hofschire, "Parenting the internet," *Journal of Communication*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 486–504, Sep. 2006, doi: 10.1111/j.1460-2466.2006.00297.x.
- [52] J. G. Smetana, "Adolescents' social reasoning and relationships with parents: Conflicts and coordinations within and across domains," in *Adolescent Vulnerabilities and Opportunities: Developmental and Constructivist Perspectives*, E. Amsel and J. Smetana, Eds., in Interdisciplinary Approaches to Knowledge and Development, Cambridge University Press, 2011, pp. 139–158.
- [53] J.-B. Pavani, S. Le Vigouroux, J.-L. Kop, A. Congard, and B. Dauvier, "Affect and affect regulation strategies reciprocally influence each other in daily life: The case of positive reappraisal, problem-focused coping, appreciation and rumination," *Journal of Happiness Studies*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 2077–2095, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s10902-015-9686-9.
- [54] E. Gracia, M. C. Fuentes, F. Garcia, and M. Lila, "Perceived neighborhood violence, parenting styles, and developmental outcomes among Spanish adolescents," *Journal of Community Psychology*, vol. 40, no. 8, pp. 1004–1021, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1002/jcop.21512.
- [55] K. L. S. Neumeister and H. Finch, "Perfectionism in high-ability students: Relational precursors and influences on achievement motivation," *Gifted Child Quarterly*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 238–251, Jul. 2006, doi: 10.1177/001698620605000304.
- [56] V. Pilarinos and C. R. Solomon, "Parenting styles and adjustment in gifted children," *Gifted Child Quarterly*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 87–98, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1177/0016986216675351.
- [57] A. L. Miller, A. D. Lambert, and K. L. Speirs Neumeister, "Parenting style, perfectionism, and creativity in high-ability and high-achieving young adults," *Journal for the Education of the Gifted*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 344–365, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.1177/0162353212459257.
- [58] F. Garcia and E. Gracia, "Is always authoritative the optimum parenting style? Evidence from Spanish families," *Adolescence*, vol. 44, no. 173, pp. 101–131, 2009.
- [59] F. Garcia and E. Gracia, "What is the optimum parental socialisation style in Spain? A study with children and adolescents aged 10–14 years," *Journal for the Study of Education and Development*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 365–384, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1174/021037010792215118.
- [60] G. Jutengren and K. Palmérus, "The potential role of conflict resolution schemas in adolescent psychosocial adjustment," *Social Indicators Research*, vol. 83, no. 1, pp. 25–38, Aug. 2007, doi: 10.1007/s11205-006-9066-2.
- [61] B. R. E. Wright, A. Caspi, T. E. Moffitt, and R. Paternoster, "Does the perceived risk of punishment deter criminally prone individuals? Rational choice, self-control, and crime," *Journal of Research in Crime and Delinquency*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 180–213, May 2004, doi: 10.1177/0022427803260263.
- [62] M. R. Gottfredson, "The empirical status of control theory in criminology," in *Taking Stock: The Status of Criminological Theory: Advances in Criminological Theory*, New York: Routledge, 2017, pp. 77–100. doi: 10.4324/9781315130620-3.
- [63] R. C. Meldrum, G. M. Connolly, J. Flexon, and R. T. Guerette, "Parental low self-control, family environments, and juvenile delinquency," *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, vol. 60, no. 14, pp. 1623–1644, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1177/0306624X15584907.
- [64] S.-J. Yeon and S. F. Messner, "Korean criminology: Juvenile delinquency and self-control theory," in *Comparative Criminology in Asia*, J. Liu, M. Travers, and L. Y. C. Chang, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 89–100. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-54942-2_7.
- [65] J. T. Ward, M. R. Nobles, and K. A. Fox, "Disentangling self-control from its elements: A bifactor analysis," *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 595–627, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s10940-014-9241-6.
- [66] S. H. Decker and D. Pyrooz, "Gang offending and online behavior," *JRSA FORUM*, vol. 30, pp. 1–5, 2012.
- [67] S. W. Baron, D. R. Forde, and F. M. Kay, "Self-control, risky lifestyles, and situation: The role of opportunity and context in the general theory," *Journal of Criminal Justice*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 119–136, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2007.01.001.
- [68] E. Cauffman, L. Steinberg, and A. R. Piquero, "Psychological, neuropsychological and physiological correlates of serious antisocial behavior in adolescence: The role of self-control," *Criminology*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 133–176, Feb. 2005, doi: 10.1111/j.0011-1348.2005.00005.x.
- [69] P. Manzoni and C. Schwarzenegger, "The influence of earlier parental violence on juvenile delinquency: The role of social bonds, self-control, delinquent peer association and moral values as mediators," *European Journal on Criminal Policy and Research*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 225–239, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10610-018-9392-3.
- [70] H. J. Janssen, V. I. Eichelsheim, M. Deković, and G. J. N. Bruinsma, "How is parenting related to adolescent delinquency? A between- and within-person analysis of the mediating role of self-control, delinquent attitudes, peer delinquency, and time spent in criminogenic settings," *European Journal of Criminology*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 169–194, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1177/1477370815608881.
- [71] R. L. Simons, L. G. Simons, Y. Chen, G. H. Brody, and K. Lin, "Identifying the psychological factors that mediate the association between parenting practices and delinquency," *Criminology*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 481–517, Aug. 2007, doi: 10.1111/j.1745-9125.2007.00086.x.
- [72] C. L. Chapple, K. A. Tyler, and B. E. Bersani, "Child neglect and adolescent violence: Examining the effects of self-control and peer rejection," *Violence and Victims*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 39–53, Feb. 2005, doi: 10.1891/vivi.2005.20.1.39.

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